

HellasQCI

Deploying advanced national QCI systems and networks in Greece

Deliverable D6.4

Report on the HellasQCI Community Establishment – final version

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Abstract: This deliverable constitutes the final report on the HellasQCI Community under Task 6.2 of Work Package 6. Building on Deliverable D6.3, it documents the transition from community establishment to community consolidation, culminating in the publication of the HellasQCI Community Joint Statement – a public document expressing the shared strategic vision of national stakeholders regarding quantum-secure communications in Greece. The deliverable presents the engagement activities and mechanisms through which consolidation was achieved, analyses the strategic orientation and key messages of the Joint Statement, addresses its publication and communication value, and outlines the sustainability and next steps of the Community beyond the project. The Joint Statement is included in its entirety. Together, the activities and outputs documented in this deliverable demonstrate the successful achievement of Milestone MS21 and confirm the HellasQCI Community as a durable national coordination mechanism aligned with the EuroQCI initiative.

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Table of Contents

Document Revision History.....	2
List of Acronyms.....	4
Executive Summary.....	5
1. Introduction	6
1.1 Relation to the project.....	6
1.2 Document Structure.....	7
2. From Community Establishment to Community Consolidation	8
2.1 Background and purpose of the HellasQCI Community Consolidation.....	8
2.2 Stakeholder engagement and community building	8
2.3 Training and flagship events as consolidation drivers.....	9
2.4 Strategic roles and boundaries of the HellasQCI Community	10
2.5 Purpose and rationale of the HellasQCI Community Joint Statement	11
3. The HellasQCI Community Joint Statement.....	12
3.1 Publication of the Joint Statement.....	12
3.2 Communication value of the Joint Statement.....	13
3.3 Key Messages Emerging from the Joint Statement.....	13
4. Sustainability and Next Steps.....	17
4.1 Sustaining the HellasQCI Community beyond the project	17
4.2 Future role in training, experimentation, and innovation	17
4.3 Alignment with national and European priorities	18
5. Conclusion.....	19

List of Acronyms

QCI	Quantum Communication Infrastructure
CSA	Coordination and support action
QKD	Quantum Key Distribution
WP	Work package
NatQCI	National QCI project
DCB	Dissemination and Communication Board
EuroQCI	European Quantum Communication infrastructure
PETRUS	EuroQCI coordination and support action
OGS	Optical ground station

Executive Summary

The HellasQCI project represents Greece’s National Quantum Communication Infrastructure (NatQCI) and a key national contribution to the European Quantum Communication Infrastructure (EuroQCI). Beyond its technical and infrastructure achievements, the project has invested consistently in building a structured national community of stakeholders capable of using, testing, developing, and exploiting the capabilities of the infrastructure over the long term.

Deliverable D6.3 “Report on the HellasQCI community establishment” documented the establishment of the HellasQCI Community, covering stakeholder mapping, the creation of the community registry, online engagement mechanisms, and the key activities through which the Community was progressively formed. The present deliverable, D6.4, reports on the final consolidation phase of this process and provides the principal output of that phase: the HellasQCI Community Joint Statement.

The consolidation of the Community was achieved through sustained training and flagship events, targeted stakeholder interactions, and ongoing communication activities. Three major training events in Athens (2023), Heraklion (2024), and Thessaloniki (2025) collectively trained over 1,000 participants across academic, research, public-sector, and industrial audiences. QCI Days 2025, held in Athens in April 2025, served as the flagship community-building event, attracting more than 600 participants from over 30 countries and providing the principal forum through which the Community’s shared strategic vision was collectively shaped. HellasQCI also participated in the LUX4QCI Liaison Workshop in May 2026, further extending its European engagement. The community registry currently comprises 41 members from 37 organisations across governmental, academic, industrial, SME, and international categories.

The HellasQCI Community Joint Statement is the central output of D6.4 and the formal evidence of Milestone MS21. It captures the shared understanding developed among stakeholders throughout the project regarding the strategic value of HellasQCI, the role of the Community, and the future direction of quantum-secure communications in Greece. It positions HellasQCI as both a national infrastructure project and a platform for experimentation, innovation, training, cybersecurity preparedness, and alignment with European quantum communication priorities.

The deliverable also addresses the publication and communication value of the Joint Statement, the sustainability mechanisms for the Community beyond the project, and the alignment of future activities with Greece’s National Quantum Strategy and the EuroQCI initiative. Together, the activities and outputs documented in this deliverable confirm the HellasQCI Community as a durable national coordination mechanism and a strategic asset for Greece’s secure digital future.

1. Introduction

HellasQCI is a European project, supported in part (50%) by the European Union under grant agreement No 101091504. The project is also supported by the Greek Government through the Ministry of Digital Governance. HellasQCI is coordinated by GRNET S.A. – National Infrastructures for Research and Technology and consists of a 14-partner consortium.

The project will design and implement the first Greek national experimental quantum communication network in three major urban centers and make it interoperable with the space segment of the EuroQCI. The deployed networks will serve as the backbone of the Hellenic national quantum infrastructure on which a diverse range of use cases and pilot scenarios will be investigated in order to introduce ultra-secure encryption of sensitive data and communication, through the use of Quantum Key Distribution (QKD) technology, in the governmental, industrial and research sectors.

This deliverable is part of Work Package 6 (WP6) “Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation”, specifically Task 6.2 “National Stakeholders Involvement – HellasQCI Community”. It reports on the final phase of community development and builds directly upon Deliverable D6.3 (“Report on the HellasQCI Community Establishment”, March 2026), which documented the establishment process in full. Readers seeking the complete account of stakeholder mapping methodology, the registry creation process, and the full chronology of engagement activities are referred to D6.3.

The primary objective of D6.4 is to document the consolidation of the HellasQCI Community and to publish the HellasQCI Community Joint Statement. This public document expresses the shared understanding among community stakeholders regarding the strategic role of HellasQCI and the future direction of quantum-secure communications in Greece. Its publication constitutes the principal evidence for the achievement of Milestone MS21 “HellasQCI Community Joint Statement”.

1.1 Relation to the project

Work Package 6 of the HellasQCI project is dedicated to the “Communication dissemination and Exploitation” activities of the consortium and its core objectives are a) to increase awareness about the project activities, outcomes and benefits , b) ensure the involvement of National stakeholders and create

Figure 1 Dissemination and Communication WP relative to other WPs

the HellasQCI community, c) support exploitation of the project results by allowing open access to selected HellasQCI tools and d) support standardization activities of the project results in European and international SDOs. Work package 6 is led by the National Centre for Scientific Research Demokritos (NCSR) while 9 other members of the consortium participate in its activities. Deliverable 6.1 is associated with task 6.1 (T6.1) of WP6 suitably named “Outreach, Communication and Exploitation plan” with 3 (GRNET, QUBITECH, NCSR) participants from the consortium.

1.2 Document Structure

The document is organized as follows:

- Section 1 presents the project introduction and Deliverable scope and purpose.
- Section 2 recapitulates some of the basic parts of D6.3 and discusses how the community was consolidated with the drafting of the HellasQCI Community Joint Statement.
- Section 3 discusses and presents in its entirety the HellasQCI Community Joint Statement.
- Section 4 proposes the sustainability of the HellasQCI community post-project and next steps.
- Section 5 is the conclusions section of this deliverable.

2. From Community Establishment to Community Consolidation

2.1 Background and purpose of the HellasQCI Community Consolidation

Deliverable D6.3 “Report on the HellasQCI Community Establishment” documented the establishment of the HellasQCI Community as a structured national stakeholder network supporting the deployment, adoption, and long-term sustainability of quantum communication infrastructures in Greece. It presented the conceptual scope of the Community, the stakeholder mapping methodology followed by the project, the creation of the community registry and online entry point, and the main engagement activities through which the Community was progressively formed.

Building on this foundation, the present deliverable reports on the final consolidation phase of the HellasQCI Community. While the initial phase focused on identifying relevant stakeholders, raising awareness, creating engagement channels, and establishing mechanisms for participation, the final phase places emphasis on the maturation of the Community into a more coherent national ecosystem. In this context, consolidation refers not only to the growth of the Community in numerical terms, but also to the emergence of a shared understanding among stakeholders regarding the strategic role of HellasQCI for Greece’s quantum communication capabilities, cybersecurity preparedness, innovation potential, and contribution to the EuroQCI initiative.

2.2 Stakeholder engagement and community building

The HellasQCI Community was established through a phased and multi-level engagement approach. At the first level, broad dissemination and awareness-raising activities introduced HellasQCI to relevant national and European audiences. At the second level, dedicated training activities enabled deeper engagement with academic, technical, industrial, and public-sector audiences, supporting the development of common knowledge and skills around QKD, PQC, cybersecurity integration, and quantum communication infrastructures. At the third level, targeted interactions with strategically relevant stakeholders supported the alignment of HellasQCI with specific user needs, operational contexts, and future exploitation pathways.

A central element of the establishment phase was the creation of dedicated mechanisms for structured participation. The HellasQCI Community section on the project website provided a visible entry point for interested stakeholders, while the online registration mechanism enabled the creation of a community registry. These tools transformed the Community from a general dissemination audience into a more durable stakeholder network, capable of supporting continued communication, targeted outreach, and long-term community management. The registry currently comprises 41 members from 36 organisations across governmental, academic, industrial, SME, research, and international categories.

Figure 2: The HellasQCI Community composition

2.3 Training and flagship events as consolidation drivers

The training programme of HellasQCI played a particularly important role in the transition from awareness to consolidation. Three major training events were organised during the project:

- HellasQCI Training Event – Athens (September 2023): A four-day event on QKD, cybersecurity, and PQC, with 375 attendees, 20 lessons, and 4 hands-on laboratory sessions.
- HellasQCI Training Event – Heraklion, Crete (September 2024): A two-day advanced event with 415 attendees, 40 expert speakers from 14 countries, hands-on demonstrations, and cross-project participation from PETRUS CSA and other National QCIs.
- HellasQCI Winter School – Thessaloniki (November 2025): A three-day event under the auspices of the Hellenic Ministry of Digital Governance and Artificial Intelligence, with approximately 250 participants and 40 international speakers from 15 countries, addressing both terrestrial and space-based QKD technologies.

Across all training activities, HellasQCI organised 9 training events, delivered 20 full days of training, performed 75 lessons, and trained more than 1,000 people. All events were held in hybrid format and made available through the HellasQCI online training platform, which includes 19 courses published on the GÉANT eAcademy.

In parallel, QCI Days 2025 (Athens, April 2025) served as the flagship community-consolidation event, attracting more than 600 participants from over 30 countries. Through policy discussions, technical sessions, live cross-border QKD demonstrations, company showcases, and a dedicated community panel, the event reinforced the role of HellasQCI as both a national infrastructure initiative and a platform for wider ecosystem development. It demonstrated that the Community had evolved beyond initial awareness raising, becoming a space for strategic dialogue and positioning within the broader EuroQCI landscape. The discussions and strategic positioning developed during QCI Days 2025 provided the principal foundation for the subsequent development of the HellasQCI Community Joint Statement.

Figure 3: The HellasQCI Community Engagement & Consolidation timeline

2.4 Strategic roles and boundaries of the HellasQCI Community

The HellasQCI Community functions as a bridge between infrastructure deployment and long-term adoption, helping ensure that HellasQCI remains aligned with real stakeholder needs, national priorities, and European developments. As Greece’s National Quantum Communication Infrastructure, HellasQCI provides a practical framework through which public authorities, research institutions, industry, SMEs, critical infrastructure operators, and cybersecurity stakeholders can explore the operational, technical, and strategic implications of quantum-secure communications.

At the same time, the Community remains defined by appropriate boundaries. Its purpose is to support awareness, training, capacity building, technical exchange at an appropriate level of abstraction, and collaboration on research, innovation, and exploitation. Security-sensitive operational details, classified information, and restricted deployment aspects remain outside the scope of community-level activities and are handled through the relevant governance and security frameworks. This distinction allows for broad and inclusive participation without compromising the confidentiality and security requirements inherent to quantum communication infrastructures and national security use cases.

2.5 Purpose and rationale of the HellasQCI Community Joint Statement

The HellasQCI Community Joint Statement represents the principal output of the final consolidation phase. It was prepared to capture, in a concise and public form, the shared understanding developed among stakeholders throughout the project regarding the strategic value of HellasQCI, the role of the Community, and the future direction of quantum-secure communications in Greece.

The rationale was twofold. First, the Joint Statement formally articulates the role of the HellasQCI Community as a multi-stakeholder ecosystem bringing together public authorities, national security bodies, critical infrastructure operators, research and academic institutions, industry, start-ups, SMEs, and other relevant actors. Second, it communicates the wider significance of the Community beyond the immediate implementation of the infrastructure, highlighting its expected contribution to long-term adoption, exploitation, and sustainability.

The Joint Statement positions HellasQCI as Greece’s National Quantum Communication Infrastructure and a key national contribution to EuroQCI, connecting the technical deployment of quantum-secure networks with broader strategic objectives: national cybersecurity, digital sovereignty, innovation, industrial development, and European cooperation. A central message is that quantum communication infrastructures cannot be sustained through technical deployment alone – their impact depends on the active participation of users, operators, researchers, technology providers, and policymakers who can transform infrastructure capabilities into operational services and strategic value.

The Joint Statement also highlights the role of HellasQCI in supporting Greece’s emerging National Quantum Strategy. By bringing together stakeholders from government, research, industry, and critical infrastructure sectors, the Community provides a concrete mechanism through which national priorities in quantum communication can be discussed, refined, and progressively implemented.

3. The HellasQCI Community Joint Statement

The HellasQCI Community Joint Statement represents the main output of the final consolidation phase of the HellasQCI Community. It was prepared in order to capture, in a concise and public form, the shared understanding developed among stakeholders throughout the project regarding the strategic value of HellasQCI, the role of the Community, and the future direction of quantum-secure communications in Greece.

The publication of the Joint Statement marks an important step in the evolution of the HellasQCI Community. While earlier activities focused on awareness raising, stakeholder mapping, training, and engagement, the Joint Statement provides a common reference point for the Community's strategic orientation. It expresses the collective recognition that HellasQCI is not only a technical deployment project, but also a national platform for experimentation, innovation, skills development, cybersecurity preparedness, and alignment with European quantum communication priorities.

The rationale for preparing the Joint Statement was therefore twofold. First, it provided a means to formally articulate the role of the HellasQCI Community as a multi-stakeholder ecosystem bringing together public authorities, national security bodies, critical infrastructure operators, research and academic institutions, industry, start-ups, SMEs, and other relevant actors. Second, it enabled the project to communicate the wider significance of the Community beyond the immediate implementation of the HellasQCI infrastructure, highlighting its expected contribution to long-term adoption, exploitation, and sustainability.

3.1 Publication of the Joint Statement

The HellasQCI Community Joint Statement was prepared as a public document expressing the shared vision, priorities, and strategic orientation of the HellasQCI Community. Its publication constitutes the principal final output of the community consolidation process and provides a formal reference point for the continued development of the Community beyond the initial establishment phase.

The Joint Statement was published through the HellasQCI communication channels and made available to stakeholders as part of the project's broader dissemination and engagement activities. By publishing the document publicly, HellasQCI ensures that the role and objectives of the Community are visible not only to existing members, but also to potential future stakeholders from the public sector, academia, research, industry, SMEs, start-ups, cybersecurity organisations, critical infrastructure operators, and European quantum communication initiatives.

The publication also strengthens the transparency and accessibility of the HellasQCI Community. It clarifies the Community's purpose, confirms its relevance for national and European quantum communication priorities, and provides a concise articulation of the expected long-term value of the HellasQCI infrastructure. In this way, the Joint Statement functions both as a dissemination output and as a strategic communication tool.

The HellasQCI Community Joint Statement was published on the HellasQCI website as a public document and the Zenodo repository. It can be retrieved from the following links:

<https://hellasqci.eu/hellasqci-community-joint-statement/>

<https://zenodo.org/records/19382870>

3.2 Communication value of the Joint Statement

The Joint Statement has communication value beyond the publication of a single document. It provides a concise and accessible narrative that can be reused in future dissemination activities, presentations, policy discussions, stakeholder meetings, training activities, and exploitation-oriented exchanges. It translates the technical and strategic objectives of HellasQCI into a common message that can be understood by diverse audiences, including technical experts, decision-makers, public authorities, industry representatives, and potential users.

In particular, the Joint Statement communicates that HellasQCI is not limited to the deployment of technical infrastructure, but is also a national platform for experimentation, training, innovation, cyber resilience, and coordinated stakeholder engagement. This message is essential for ensuring that the infrastructure is understood as a long-term national asset, capable of supporting both operational cybersecurity needs and future research and industrial development.

3.3 Key Messages Emerging from the Joint Statement

Before reproducing the Joint Statement in full, this subsection summarises its principal messages, categorised in five strategic priorities:

- **Cybersecurity and cyber resilience:** The Statement frames quantum-secure communications as an urgent response to the threat that quantum computing poses to classical cryptography, positioning HellasQCI as a strategic pillar of Greece's cybersecurity architecture for protecting governmental communications and critical infrastructure (energy, healthcare) and contributing to European digital sovereignty.
- **Innovation and industrial development:** The statement commits the Community to building a national value chain, using the HellasQCI infrastructure to help academia translate research into deployable technology, support start-ups and SMEs, and enable industry to co-develop interoperable products, impacting competitiveness and skilled employment.
- **Skills and capacity building:** Training is treated as a permanent, structured process rather than a one-off effort, combining in-person events with a digital training platform to sustain a national pool of professionals in quantum and post-quantum security technologies.
- **National strategy:** HellasQCI is positioned as a concrete mechanism supporting Greece's emerging National Quantum Strategy, calling for a structured governance model and a forward-looking policy roadmap for the coordinated adoption of QKD alongside PQC.
- **EuroQCI alignment:** HellasQCI is affirmed as a key national contribution to EuroQCI, committed to interoperable, future-proof solutions and continued knowledge exchange with other National QCI initiatives and European stakeholders.

The HellasQCI Community Joint Statement is reproduced in its entirety below.

HellasQCI Community Joint Statement

Enabling Quantum Secure Communications, Innovation, and Cyber Resilience in Greece

1. Introduction and Strategic Context

HellasQCI constitutes Greece’s National Quantum Communication Infrastructure (NatQCI) and a key national contribution to the European Quantum Communication Infrastructure (EuroQCI). Beyond the technical deployment of quantum secure networks, the long-term success and sustainability of HellasQCI depend on the existence of a structured national community capable of actively using, testing, evolving, and exploiting the network’s capabilities.

The HellasQCI Community is conceived as a national, multi-stakeholder ecosystem bringing together public authorities, national security bodies, critical infrastructure operators, industry, academia, start-ups, and SMEs. Its objective is to facilitate the diffusion and adoption of quantum communication technologies across Greece, consolidate national expertise, and promote the uptake of secure, interoperable, and future-proof communication solutions aligned with European priorities.

This Joint Statement reflects the shared understanding among participating stakeholders regarding the strategic value of a structured national community, the influence of HellasQCI in shaping Greece’s upcoming National Quantum Strategy (as presented and supported in the QCI Days 2025 event), the role of HellasQCI as both an operational and experimental platform, and the importance of sustained training and capacity building in the domain of quantum secure communications.

To support visibility and engagement, a dedicated community page has been developed within the HellasQCI portal, serving as a central entry point for information, updates, and resources.

2. Formation of the HellasQCI Community

The HellasQCI project kick-off in January 2023 marked the formal alignment of governmental stakeholders, national security authorities, academic institutions, and industrial partners around a common vision for quantum secure communications. This early engagement ensured that cybersecurity requirements, operational constraints, and innovation objectives were embedded from the initial phases of infrastructure deployment-

Community building was further strengthened through a series of structured national training programmes organised in Athens (September 2023), Crete (September 2024), and Thessaloniki (November 2025). These activities addressed policy and governance aspects, cybersecurity integration, technical deployment and operation of Quantum Key Distribution (QKD) systems, interoperability challenges, and the role of experimental infrastructures, including optical ground stations and space-based QKD technologies. The trainings targeted public sector operators, cybersecurity professionals, researchers, engineers, and industrial stakeholders, fostering a shared technical and operational understanding across regions and sectors.

In April 2025, the QCI Days event served as a national focal point for the HellasQCI Community, bringing together Greek and European stakeholders, showcasing deployment progress and experimental capabilities, and reinforcing Greece’s active role within the wider EuroQCI ecosystem.

3. Role of an Experimental Quantum Communication Infrastructure

A core pillar of the HellasQCI Community is the availability of an experimental quantum communication infrastructure accessible to both public and private sector entities. This infrastructure enables the testing, validation, and benchmarking of QKD and hybrid QKD – Post Quantum Cryptography (PQC) solutions under realistic operational conditions. The experimental environment supports interoperability testing, network orchestration, and the demonstration of secure communication use cases relevant to governmental bodies and critical infrastructure operators. It allows stakeholders to move beyond theoretical research and isolated pilots by experimenting with real operational constraints, security policies, and performance requirements in a trusted national setting.

4. Supporting Innovation and Industrial Development

The HellasQCI Community actively supports the development of a national quantum communications value chain. By providing access to advanced infrastructure and research capabilities, HellasQCI enables Greek academic institutions to translate research outcomes into deployable technologies, supports startups and SMEs in developing and maturing quantum-secure solutions, and allows industrial actors to codevelop interoperable products aligned with national and European requirements. This collaborative framework strengthens national synergies, encourages cross sector partnerships, and promotes the uptake and commercialisation of quantum communication technologies within the Greek economy.

Beyond technology development, this multi-stakeholder ecosystem is expected to generate measurable impact on the Greek economy by enabling new high-value products and services, strengthening competitiveness, and supporting skilled job creation across the quantum-secure communications value chain. At the same time, it signals to the European Union that Greece is moving towards utilising the quantum technologies—advancing from readiness and pilots to coordinated adoption, industrial capacity, and long-term strategic participation in Europe’s quantum-secure digital future.

5. Training and Capacity Building

Quantum secure communications require sustained investment in skills, expertise, and operational readiness. The rapid evolution of quantum technologies, combined with the anticipated impact of quantum computing on existing cryptographic systems, makes continuous training a strategic necessity. HellasQCI therefore treats capacity building as a permanent and structured process. In addition to in person training activities, a dedicated digital training [platform](#) provides continuous access to educational material, recorded sessions, technical documentation, and best practices. This blended approach strengthens national preparedness, ensures the secure operation of quantum communication infrastructures, and creates skilled professionals in quantum and post-quantum security technologies.

6. Contribution to Cybersecurity and Critical Infrastructure Protection

HellasQCI directly addresses national and European cybersecurity priorities at a time when the protection of sensitive data and critical digital infrastructure has become a strategic imperative. The increasing sophistication of cyber threats, together with the foreseeable impact of quantum computing on classical cryptography, makes the transition to quantum-secure communications an urgent requirement.

Quantum technologies are essential for safeguarding governmental and national security communications and for enabling the secure interconnection of critical infrastructures, including energy, transport, healthcare, and financial systems. By combining infrastructure deployment, experimental validation, continuous training, and coordinated stakeholder engagement, the HellasQCI Community forms a strategic pillar of Greece’s cybersecurity architecture and contributes to European digital sovereignty objectives.

7. Looking Ahead: Governance, Policy, and Future Development

As quantum communication technologies mature and gain strategic importance, the long-term success of HellasQCI depends on the continued strengthening of its organisational, policy, and technical foundations. Looking ahead, the HellasQCI community recognises the value of establishing a structured governance model that ensures balanced representation of governmental bodies, national security authorities, critical infrastructure operators, academia, research institutions, and industry, enabling inclusive participation, effective coordination, and coherent decision-making.

In parallel, the community highlights the need for a forward-looking policy roadmap supporting the adoption and operational integration of quantum communication technologies such as QKD, in tandem with PQC solutions. Such a roadmap should align with national cybersecurity priorities and European strategic objectives, with the Greek National Quantum Strategy providing the overarching framework. The HellasQCI community can contribute to refining this strategy and supporting the definition of concrete implementation actions.

Finally, the sustained evolution of the HellasQCI experimental infrastructure remains a strategic priority. Developing a roadmap for future phases, including testbed extensions, advanced experimentation environments, and additional real-world use cases, will ensure that the infrastructure continues to support research, innovation, training, and operational validation while contributing to the broader EuroQCI vision.

8. Conclusion

This Joint Statement confirms the shared commitment of stakeholders to the HellasQCI Community as a core element of Greece’s National Quantum Communication Infrastructure. The Community is recognised as a key mechanism for ensuring the active use, continuous testing, and progressive evolution of the infrastructure in line with operational and strategic needs.

Through coordinated engagement, experimentation, and capacity building, the HellasQCI Community is expected to maximise the long-term value and strategic impact of Greece’s quantum communication capabilities, supporting a secure, resilient, and trusted digital future.

4. Sustainability and Next Steps

4.1 Sustaining the HellasQCI Community beyond the project

The establishment and consolidation of the HellasQCI Community provide a foundation for continued stakeholder engagement beyond the initial project implementation period. Maintaining this network is important for ensuring that the results of HellasQCI continue to generate value after the project's completion.

The sustainability of the Community depends on the continued use of the engagement mechanisms developed during HellasQCI. The community registry, online entry point, training platform, dissemination channels, and stakeholder contacts provide practical tools for maintaining communication, sharing updates, promoting new opportunities, and supporting future collaboration. These mechanisms can help ensure that the Community remains active and responsive to new developments in quantum communications, cybersecurity, and EuroQCI deployment.

The HellasQCI Community should continue to function as a national forum for awareness raising, capacity building, technical exchange, and stakeholder feedback, while remaining complementary to formal governance, operational, and security structures. Its continuity will also be directly supported by the Phase 2 EuroQCI projects – [SEEWQCI](#) and TransEuroOGS – which started in 2026 and in which several HellasQCI community members and consortium partners are actively involved.

4.2 Future role in training, experimentation, and innovation

Training and capacity building will remain central to the future role of the HellasQCI Community. Quantum communication technologies are evolving rapidly, and their integration with existing cybersecurity architectures, post-quantum cryptography, network management systems, and operational infrastructures requires continuous skills development. The HellasQCI training platform and the experience gained from the Athens, Heraklion, and Thessaloniki training events provide a strong basis for future educational activities, specialised workshops, and targeted sessions for different stakeholder groups.

The Community can also continue to support experimentation and validation through the HellasQCI infrastructure. As a national experimental platform, HellasQCI can enable stakeholders to test quantum-secure communication solutions, explore hybrid QKD and post-quantum cryptography approaches, assess interoperability, and validate use cases under realistic conditions. This experimental dimension is particularly important for bridging the gap between research, technology development, and operational adoption.

In addition, the Community can contribute to innovation and industrial development by facilitating interaction between research institutions, technology providers, SMEs, start-ups, public-sector users, and critical infrastructure operators. Such interactions can support the identification of practical needs, the co-development of solutions, and the maturation of quantum-secure products and services aligned with national and European requirements. In this way, the Community can support the emergence of a national value chain around quantum communications and related cybersecurity technologies.

4.3 Alignment with national and European priorities

The future development of the HellasQCI Community should remain closely aligned with national and European priorities. At national level, the Community can support the implementation of Greece’s quantum and cybersecurity ambitions by providing a structured channel for dialogue between policy, research, industry, and potential users. It can contribute to the refinement of priorities, the identification of practical implementation needs, and the promotion of quantum-secure communication technologies across relevant sectors.

At European level, the Community can continue to support Greece’s contribution to EuroQCI by facilitating knowledge exchange with other National QCI initiatives, relevant Coordination and Support Actions, and European stakeholders. The experience developed through HellasQCI, including training, stakeholder engagement, experimentation, and community building, can provide useful input to the wider European effort towards interoperable quantum communication infrastructures.

Looking ahead, the continued evolution of the HellasQCI infrastructure and Community may involve further testbed extensions, additional use cases, new forms of stakeholder engagement, and deeper integration with European quantum communication initiatives. These future steps will help ensure that HellasQCI remains relevant as technologies mature, operational requirements evolve, and quantum-secure communications move progressively from experimentation towards wider adoption.

5. Conclusion

Deliverable D6.4 has presented the final consolidation phase of the HellasQCI Community. Building on the establishment process documented in D6.3, the present deliverable has focused on the transition from community formation to the articulation of a shared strategic vision, expressed through the HellasQCI Community Joint Statement.

The HellasQCI Community was established as a national, multi-stakeholder ecosystem supporting the deployment, adoption, and long-term sustainability of quantum communication infrastructures in Greece. Through stakeholder mapping, dedicated engagement mechanisms, training activities, flagship events, and targeted interactions, the project succeeded in creating a structured forum for awareness raising, capacity building, technical exchange, and strategic dialogue. These activities enabled the Community to mature beyond a dissemination audience into a more coherent national ecosystem.

The publication of the HellasQCI Community Joint Statement marks the principal outcome of this final consolidation phase. The Joint Statement confirms the strategic role of the Community in supporting quantum-secure communications, cyber resilience, innovation, industrial development, training, governance dialogue, and future infrastructure evolution. It also reinforces the position of HellasQCI as Greece's National Quantum Communication Infrastructure and as an active contribution to the European Quantum Communication Infrastructure.

By including the Joint Statement in its entirety, this deliverable records the shared vision that emerged through the HellasQCI community-building process. It provides a reference point for future engagement with stakeholders, national authorities, European initiatives, and potential users of quantum-secure communication services.

Overall, the activities and outputs documented in D6.4 demonstrate that the HellasQCI Community has been successfully consolidated. The Community now provides a foundation for continued collaboration, training, experimentation, innovation, and strategic alignment, supporting the long-term value and impact of HellasQCI for Greece's secure and resilient digital future.